

Desire:

If I give a 5 year old a diamond wrist watch, he might throw it away and rather fight for the Ben 10 watch that he has seen on TV or other kids in the school are having.

Or

If I go to a remote village in India and throw away a million USD on the streets, nobody is gonna pick it up. Because they know it's not the currency they use everyday. They think it's fake. Even if somebody knows the value, it's impossible for them to do currency exchange.

Or

If I leave you on an island with a suitcase full of cash and block all external communication, all you can do with that cash is wipe your ass. You would rather fight for some food.

Humans don't really know what to desire. They desire what others are desiring and eventually end up in conflict and violence

As seen on TV:

If you possess something valuable by people around you, you possess fear as well. Because they can kill and take it.

It is done in such a subtle yet precise manner that nobody notices it until they're in deep shit.

As a kid, you'll watch cartoons. Your mom will be worried why you're watching insects. Your dad won't care.

Your mom will watch some soap and you get irritated.

As an adult, you'll watch porn. You'll hide from your mom and your dad will understand.

Zoo vs Safari:

All your life, you'll just switch between these two psychological states. Zoo and safari.

In zoos, animals are confined and humans roam around freely.

In Safari, humans are in confined vehicles and animals roam around freely.

In zoos, animals get food, shelter and care.

In safari, animals live as they usually do in the wild. They have to protect themselves and find food themselves.

If you're homeless and badly need shelter, clothing and food, a jail can be your heaven.

If you have a nice home and enjoy home cooked meals everyday, then jail can be hell.

If jail has better facilities than your home, then you voluntarily commit crimes and go to jail.

Prisons will be overcrowded.

If jail is worse, then you avoid doing crimes because your home is better.

See these pictures of Safari 📍.

Animals have freedom in safari. If you step out of the vehicle, they can kill you. Plus you might have to pay a fine for violating the rules. Rangers have to euthanize the animal.

And see these pictures of a zoo 🙄.

They don't have freedom.

They'll be taken care of though.

In case, if it escapes and attacks visitors, then the zoo will be held accountable for not having safety standards.

A human means a country's leader is also a human and a random tribal kid is also a human.

As a human, are you an animal that can be domesticated or you're a wild animal?

If you're a social threat, should you be killed?

In India, death sentences are rare.

You can be sentenced for life.

Do you want to be in a zoo or safari?

If your house doesn't have AC and school has, you would love to go to school.

If your school sucks and your house has AC and other amenities, you don't want to go to school.

If a jail has a private AC room, TV, WIFI, hot tub etc, you would love to be in jail. In fact, you'll compete to be in jail.

Jails will be overcrowded and you might be house arrested instead.

People constantly try to get to know you. Because they want to know whether you're a social threat or not.

That is the sole purpose of knowing and understanding the other person.

That's exactly what I'm against.

For me, freedom has ultimate value. There is nothing higher than freedom.

Identity:

Just think of this situation.

There is a city with 1 lakh population.

One day, a police officer sees a small boy being lost in the middle of the city.

The boy looked like this 🙋

He goes to him and asks him who he is? What is his name? Who are his parents? And what is his home address?

It's quite obvious that he's a human.

He might be able to tell his name.

He might be able to tell his parents names as well.

He might not be able to tell his home address.

Now, his parents are not so popular figures in the city to easily identify.

How does this police officer gonna reunite this boy with his family?

First of all, he'll take him into protective custody. See if anybody has filed a missing complaint. Parents might have filed a complaint saying he's wearing a blue tee, his age and name.

If the police officer finds a complaint, he'll call the parents to reunite this boy with his family. If no complaint has been filed, then police might make an announcement to see if someone comes.

If nobody comes forward, then he'll follow some protocol. Reporting the child to some child welfare committee or so.

The boy might end up in an orphanage or put for adoption.

Now, what if the boy looked like this 🙋 ?

Not only the police officer, anybody, even an illiterate person can tell which school he belongs to.

People might have noticed kids with similar uniforms going to a specific school.

School will be a popular building in the city.

The school details will be mentioned on the belt, tie and even in the logo on the shirt.

If he's wearing an id card, then the boy details also will be mentioned.

It'll be very easy to identify.

From the school, parents will pick up or the school bus will drop.

With the uniform it'll be easy to identify who a person is

You know that these are police 🙋 .

You know that these are traffic cops 🙋 .

You know that this is prisoner 🙄.

You know these are zepto delivery guys 🙄.

You might know these are Ayyappan devotees 🙏.

You know these are monks 🙏.

You know these are muslim 🙏.

If you ever played GTA, you know who these are 🙄.

If you strip off the clothes, all are humans.

You will never find out who is who. Max you can find out the gender.

5 minutes after your birth, they decide your name, nationality and religion.
You spend the rest of your life defending something that you didn't even choose.

Cross-race effect:

Saw this meme before?

**When you get robbed in China
And police ask you
"What they looked like?"**

The cross-race effect (CRE), or other-race bias, is the well-documented phenomenon where individuals are better at recognizing and identifying faces of their own race compared to faces of other races.

That's why you think all Chinese look the same.

All sheep look the same. All cows look the same. All buffaloes look the same.

Even animals will identify one of their own as it's needed for mating.
Most of the creatures identify their partner and babies as well.

Micro vs Macro:

There are way too many movies in this genre.

If you can build something with lego blocks, you build real things.

If you can light a match box, you can set fire to an entire forest.

If you can send a Diwali rocket up, you can launch a real rocket.

If you can blast a Diwali bomb, then you can blast a real bomb.

If you can navigate GTA games, you can navigate any city, any park, any country.

If you can drive a toy car, you can drive a real car.

We have the sea. You can have an aquarium.

We have the earth. You can have a globe on your desk or Google earth on your phone.

It's just that you need larger quantities.

A glass of water can't do any harm. But an ocean can.

A match box or a lighter might not cause any major harm but a wild fire can.

A small quantity of gunpowder won't cause much damage. But larger quantities do.

A toy car won't do any harm but a real car can kill people.

A small amount of cash will give you some buying power. But large amounts of cash can disrupt the society.

Cost of life:

The company I work for has around **10,000** employees.
Every year we waste **1000rs** each on **stupid ass secret santa**.

The entire money gets circulated within the company.

10000 * 1000 = 1Cr

If I get a serious illness which costs **1Cr** to cure, I can request a fund raiser with my employer.

My employer already provides me a health insurance of **6L** which covers family size up to 4 members

I have my own personal health insurance for **30L**.

My employer has group life insurance which covers my life.

I have my own term life insurance for **1cr**.

Even if I get an illness which costs just **30L** and my personal health insurance covers it, I'll still deny the treatment and rather choose to die.

Because what is the point of living with a treatment worth **30L**?

Even if you offer me free treatment worth crores of rupees, still I choose to die.

Marriage & Kids:

Listen to the master of masters Osho.

Listen to Puri Musings.

Listen to RGV.

Don't get married.

Instead of doing business with an Indian priest do with a Thai Priest.

They're very good at their business.

Connections:

Dunbar's number is a proposed cognitive limit of approximately 150 individuals with whom a human can maintain stable, meaningful social relationships.

Let's throw a 100 more to it and make 250 maximum.

All your enemies, friends and relatives will be from this 250 people only.

To give you a rough idea, see the pictures below.

The left side image is the seating layout of KSRTC AIRAVAT CLUB CLASS 2.0. And the right side image is of the bus.

All your connections can fit into 5 such buses.

KSRTC alone has a fleet of 8199 buses.

If you just leave this 150 or 250 circle, nobody would recognise you.

Familiarity breeds contempt.

The bus operator won't care whether you're rich/poor/black/white/caste/nationality anything. He'll sell the bus ticket to anybody who pays money.

It could be anything. A mobile phone manufacturer will sell mobile phones to anybody who pays.

No business will show discrimination. It's legally not allowed to show discrimination.

All this jealousy, hatred, discrimination happens within your 150 or 250 connections.

Since you feel so helpless and can't escape this circle, you'll start doing unpaid acting.

Boundaries:

There are no geographical boundaries.

All the states do business with all the states.

All the countries do business with all the countries.

It's exactly the same Volvo bus.

If KSRTC buys it and puts the KSRTC brand, it'll become a KSRTC bus.

If TSRTC buys it and puts the TSRTC brand, it'll become a TSRTC bus.

If some private bus operator buys it and puts their own branding, then it'll be a private travel bus.

You can travel from Bangalore to Hyderabad or Hyderabad to Mumbai.

India does business with other countries and other countries do business with India.

We have airlines to all the countries.

Death:

When I was a kid, there used to be a broadcast of Bhagavad Gita from a temple nearby.

"The one that is born is bound to die, and the one that is dead is bound to be reborn. We should not bother much about this inevitable nature of life"

Compassionate leave is unnecessary. If you cry or mourn, will the dead come alive?

Death is something that should be celebrated not mourned.

And you die just like any other animal.

Age limits:

You have an age limit to get admission into school.

You have an age limit to get voting right.

You have an age limit to smoke or drink.

You have an age limit to have sex/get married.
You have an age limit to watch certain content.
You have an age limit to play certain video games.
You have an age limit to open a bank account.
You have an age limit to get a driving license.

Expiry:

Your passport will expire.
Your driving licence will expire.
Your bank account will become inactive.
Your phone number will become inactive.
Your email id will become inactive.

Your life itself will expire.
That's why banks will keep marking your account as inactive if you don't make any transaction for a while.
If you don't use your phone number for a while, your phone number will be given to somebody else.

Recycling:

If you tonsure your hair in Tirumala, the hair will be sold in an auction.
Whatever the donations you make to Tirumala will come back to devotees like food, hospital, shelter, wigs etc.

There'll be continuous free food serving happening in Tirumala.
There are schools under TTD.
There are hospitals under TTD.

Every god or public figure tells the same thing.
Instead of wasting on me, help the other person.
We won't do it. We would rather donate to a stone or an invisible thing.
From that invisible thing it'll come back to you again.

Osho:

<https://youtu.be/5ocbZhRQS9I?si=IZigpE-FqogRKJGV>
<https://youtu.be/UngV-qwNkW0?si=sZ3XCeUvQpOkZ-DT>
<https://youtu.be/At6yK9NUnv0?si=lb5eByYqRs5fwn1D>
<https://youtu.be/RsuxPC8CIRo?si=VAv9NxZqIncEHR0k>
https://youtu.be/Q_yBolGPyME?si=8c6gGfVgrN8r3l8j

<https://youtu.be/8Plcd9q3QxU?si=TapBTAc06AjPrSiL>
<https://youtu.be/0v3OeszyaxE?si=IN1yvzw8iwDXMdKm>

Puri Musings:

<https://youtu.be/u9djslLnL2I?si=kNFPJtk-UvWBR4Gn>
https://youtu.be/t7_sXiHWpW8?si=A1TzdrHaCj64N-ci
<https://youtu.be/KobZddH77mA?si=5g0Tc-OS27E5S4Lw>
https://youtu.be/Ge6R1wV8J50?si=_KTcy8OWUxQgBiBy
<https://youtu.be/MnZhRfcaSel?si=ynDAHkcnookeSAqu>
<https://youtu.be/5pmRM4kbGZ8?si=oRRce3gDw3S.JblbX>
<https://youtu.be/5pmRM4kbGZ8?si=UoGMmlB4FY3ZtteX>
https://youtu.be/kfQi4wXzjog?si=tqk5KGcHg7E3_Y6S
<https://youtu.be/7DSndcM6l84?si=jvhlLu35nxGskxNV>
https://youtu.be/7DSndcM6l84?si=_AkxzwL2dS84OFwk
https://youtu.be/Y1T_HIJRhus?si=JsBJzngngfS7qBazN
<https://youtu.be/rEXNzSmvULA?si=ThQi7Y8g7SV4MUIp>
https://youtu.be/QM2hLV1Hvog?si=g9xgGtf_KroVi9Zw
<https://youtu.be/2KPSLk5x7NE?si=z4EwGQbi0jOkNo7O>
https://youtu.be/8nB_AwXklyQ?si=U9z-EHEZoaUrt8GV
<https://youtu.be/tZLLfVuSiQE?si=isBu0uec9-LGGYKL>
<https://youtu.be/LmGEXmmZ1nE?si=8GTE5JoMZwvRW1de>
<https://youtu.be/MiJCKVBlyLU?si=mpHfttho6tNxAiZd>

RGV:

https://youtu.be/bUbr5RJt76g?si=oO35z_AHyURQvPrd
<https://youtu.be/k3UK1RdTKfU?si=zNmPHOa9GxSrgYgE>
https://youtu.be/BO_n1K1QTbk?si=dL1xEeqTYuyWP7y8
<https://youtu.be/asbDPc6kklw?si=-cBgcLeNUnyeMDhd>
https://youtu.be/tH3vMSUsllc?si=Jeh576Rbvc9B6_pt
https://youtu.be/FdPsMpK2GF8?si=2Cvf_fAsOYQdQOta
https://youtu.be/Kc_U9QBoUkA?si=HTh3DDyfl_x7cYh1
<https://youtu.be/al5p5m1ivlY?si=bYxpu3JWR2niqxJu>

Sources:

Prisons : <https://eprisons.nic.in/NPIP/public/Home>
Schools : <https://dashboard.udiseplus.gov.in>
Higher Education: <https://aishe.gov.in>
Judicial data: <https://njdg.ecourts.gov.in>
Live stock: <https://bharatpashudhan.ndlm.co.in>
Vehicles: <https://vahan.parivahan.gov.in/vahan4dashboard>

What do I want?

My death to be celebrated.

Funeral Playlist:

https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLRWqhTluRpuQdcXf8HZ9_u_IK6zCW5Vqg&si=0OKRCzbMZb5VeSad

There was a beggar in Shirdi, Maharashtra. His burial site is called Samadhi Mandhir. It's fetching a lot of revenue to Maharashtra.

If that beggar's burial site is fetching that much revenue to Maharashtra, I want my place of birth to fetch even more revenue to my state and then my country and then the earth and then the universe.

And there should be a strict check that only educated, intelligent people should be allowed to visit.